

“A STUDY TO TEST THE MARKET EFFICIENCY USING RUN TEST”

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Abstract

In the past, Indian stock market was characterized as an inefficient market. In a single day, market used to have abrupt movements. There was no concept of circuit breaker for the movement of share prices in a single trading day. Several procedural and regulatory changes have been introduced in the Indian stock market to bring in efficiency in its functioning. Efficient Market Hypothesis is based on the fundamentals that markets are efficient and prices make an independent movement in these markets. The price of an individual share is independent of the previous prices; the implication of this is that price of a moment does not affect the price of another moment - this type of movement of prices is called random walk of prices and therefore, this hypothesis is also called 'Random Walk Hypothesis'.

The present study applies run test to test the market efficiency. The run test is used to test whether a market is in weak form of efficiency or not, if price movement passes this test, then the market is considered to be efficient in weak form of efficiency. The objective of the study is to test whether successive price changes of shares of IT companies included in NIFTY are independent or not during the five year period (2012-2016). The paper highlights the various forms of market efficiency. The paper checks whether Indian capital market are in weak form of efficiency, semi strong form of efficiency or strong form of efficiency.

Key Words: *Market Efficiency, run test, stock market.*

Introduction

When share prices follow an independent path we say the market is efficient. This happens because of the presence of:

- Large number of investors in the market
- Free flow of information to all the investors
- Every kind of price sensitive information is discounted in the prices immediately
- Every investor is capable enough to interpret the information
- No one is so strong to influence the market unduly.

When a market is efficient then each price of a share is independent of the previous price. Prices are influenced by the equilibrium of demand and supply. A market can be either identified as efficient or inefficient. The market efficiency totally depends on the facilities, full disclosure, transparency and regulatory provision governing the market. The Indian market was inefficient in the past due

to various factors - lack of transparency, manual trading system, delay in the settlement of trades, no protection to investors, especially small investors, etc.

Indian Stock Market Moving Towards Market Efficiency

Several procedural and regulatory changes have been introduced in the Indian stock market to bring in efficiency in its functioning. In the last 10 to 15 years changes have been introduced to achieve market efficiency:

- Automated/Online Trading System
- Depository System
- Changes in Settlement System
- Ban on Badla
- Introduction of Derivatives
- Provision of full disclosure and transparency
- Provision to check insider trading
- Corporatization of stock exchanges

Kendall examined the behaviour of stock and commodity prices in search of regular cycles. Instead of discovering any regular price cycle, he found each series to be a wandering one. In 1953, Maurice Kendall in his paper reported that stock price series is a wandering one. They appeared to be random; each successive change is independent of the previous one.

Efficient Market

- In an efficient security market, security prices adjust rapidly to the arrival of any new information, therefore the current prices of securities reflect all information related to the security.
- An efficient market is one in which the market price of a security is an unbiased estimate of its intrinsic value.
- In an efficient market the current price of a security fully reflects all available information and is the fair value.
- Market efficiency signifies how quickly and accurately does relevant information have its effect on the asset price. Depending upon the degree of efficiency of a market or a sector thereof, the return earned by an investor will vary from the normal return.

Efficient Market Hypothesis

According to EMH, successive absolute short run price changes are independent. The hypothesis is based on the assumption that the market comprises rational investors. The term rational mean that investors will select assets based on their risk return profile.

The Random Walk Theory

In simple words, we can say that the random walk theory of investment is based on the premise that there is no logic in share price movements; that prices will rise and fall on whims and by the manipulations of individuals and that there is no need to study trends and movements of prices prior to making an investment in shares.

The basic random walk premise is that price movements are totally random. On a look at the charting of share prices in many instances it can be observed that many price movements could be random. Prices have no memory; therefore past and present prices cannot be used to predict future prices. Prices move at random and adjust to new information as it becomes available. The adjustment to this new information is so fast that it is impossible to profit from it. Furthermore, news and events are also random and trying to predict this is futile.

Roberts and Osborne published two articles on the behaviour of share prices, in the year 1959. Both these articles emphasized that change in share prices exhibit a

random movement and do not follow any predictable pattern. These two articles suggested that the market is already efficient and hence there is no scope for any prediction. Studies carried out by many others also supported the view that share price movements are at random. Thus, efficient market theory which gained acceptance during 1960s was then known by the name Random Walk Theory.

The random walk hypothesis is based on following assumptions:

- Market is perfect and free without any trade restrictions
- Market absorbs all the information quickly and efficiently
- Information is free and costless and is freely available to all at the same time
- Information is fair and correct
- Market players can analyze the information quickly and it is absorbed in the market through buy and sell signals.

Categories of Market Efficiency

According to Eugene Fama, market efficiency is divided into three categories:

(a) Weak Form Efficiency

- A market is considered efficient in weak form only when each subsequent price is independent of the previous price. The prices always make a random walk and get affected only by the demand and supply position. If a market reflects such form of efficiency then Technical Analysis cannot benefit the investors in making investment decisions.
- It says that current prices fully reflect all historical information, hence any attempt to predict prices based on historical price or information is totally futile as future price changes are independent of past price changes.
- It states that current price does not reflect fair value and is only a reflection of past prices.
- This implies that past rates of return and other market data should have no relationship with future rates of return

(b) Semi Strong Form

- It is the level of efficient market in which companies, industrial houses and government follow the principle of full disclosure and transparency. Every kind of price sensitive information is made available in the market as soon as it is generated. Such information gets reflected immediately and influences the prices only during the shorter time span; it has no subsequent effect on the prices. If a market has such form of efficiency, even the fundamental analysis cannot benefit.

- It states that current stock prices reflect all publicly available information such as earnings, dividends, splits, mergers and takeovers, interest rate changes, etc. It also says that prices adjust to such information 'quickly and accurately' so abnormal profits on a consistent basis cannot be earned.
- Market efficiency in the semi strong form ignores specialist information held by insiders, competitors, contractors, suppliers or regulators, etc.
- In the case of competitive market, price is fixed by the supply and demand force. The intrinsic value of the stock and the equilibrium price are the same. When ever a new information arrives at the market, the demand and supply factors react to it. If the market has to be semi strongly efficient, timely and correct dissemination of information and assimilation of news are needed.

(c) Strong Form Efficiency

- Market is considered to be efficient in strong form when an insider is not able to gain from the information. A strong form of efficiency is achieved only when high level of disclosure standards and transparency is maintained at the end of the company; it may be obligatory or voluntary.
- It states that prices of securities fully reflect all available information - both public and private. That is, if this form is true, prices reflect the information that is available to only selected groups - like the management, financiers and stock exchange officials.
- The strong form of the efficient market hypothesis maintains that not only the publicly available information is useless to the investor or analyst but all information is useless. This implies that security analyst and portfolio managers who have access to information more quickly than the ordinary investors would not be able to use it to earn more profits.

Market efficiency level can be tested with the help of quantitative measurements. Quantitative methods like RUN test and Serial correlation test and qualitative test is through the method of observation about the disclosure and transparency measurements.

RUN Test: In order to find out the status about the form of efficiency, RUN Test is carried out. This test is used to test whether a market is in weak form of efficiency or not, if price movement passes this test, then the market is considered to be efficient in weak form of efficiency.

Objectives Of The Study

The objectives of the present study are:

- To test whether successive price changes are independent or not during the five year period ranging from 2012 to 2016
- To analyze the various categories of market efficiency
- To check whether Indian capital market are in weak form of efficiency, semi strong form of efficiency or strong form of efficiency.

Research Methodology

Research Type: Empirical

Sampling Unit: Information Technology Companies in India

Sampling Universe: All IT Companies in NIFTY

Data Type: Secondary Data

Data Source:

<http://www.moneycontrol.com/stocks/histstock.php>

Tools for analysis: Run Test

Price: Monthly closing prices are taken.

Scope of the study: The prices of the shares are during the calendar year 2012 to 2016

Hypothesis

Null Hypothesis: H_0 : Price change is random

Alternate Hypothesis: H_1 : Price change is not random

Run tests can be used to test:

- The randomness of a distribution by taking the data in the given order and marking with + the data greater than the median and with the - data less than the median (Numbers equaling the median are omitted).
- Whether a function fits well to a data set, by marking the data exceeding the function value with + and the other data with -. For this use, the runs test, which takes into account the signs but not the distances, is complementary to the chi-square test, which takes into account the distances but not the signs.

Run test statistics is a kind of non-parametric statistical test that checks a randomness hypothesis for a two valued data sequences. More precisely, run test can be used to test the hypothesis that the elements of the sequence are mutually independent one. A run of a sequence is defined as a maximal non-empty segment of the data sequence consisting of adjacent equal elements.

Table 1: Prices of shares on the last day of the month from 2012 - 2016

HCL Technologies		Infosys		TCS		Tech Mahindra		Wipro	
Days	Closing	Days	Closing	Days	Closing	Days	Closing	Days	Closing
Months	Price	Months	Price	Months	Price	Months	Price	Months	Price
Jan-12	193.63	Jan-12	685.84	Jan-12	1130.50	Jan-12	162.93	Jan-12	206.63
Feb-12	219.60	Feb-12	718.85	Feb-12	1221.05	Feb-12	150.05	Feb-12	215.88
Mar-12	242.13	Mar-12	716.24	Mar-12	1167.85	Mar-12	179.91	Mar-12	219.50
Apr-12	239.50	Apr-12	615.65	Apr-12	1244.90	Apr-12	175.05	Apr-12	202.55
May-12	260.00	May-12	609.97	May-12	1245.80	May-12	167.66	May-12	204.78
Jun-12	252.50	Jun-12	625.64	Jun-12	1277.55	Jun-12	176.99	Jun-12	199.65
Jul-12	239.50	Jul-12	556.85	Jul-12	1240.65	Jul-12	177.98	Jul-12	169.95
Aug-12	259.25	Aug-12	593.32	Aug-12	1347.30	Aug-12	199.49	Aug-12	183.80
Sep-12	273.50	Sep-12	633.50	Sep-12	1294.00	Sep-12	242.95	Sep-12	190.65
Oct-12	288.40	Oct-12	590.88	Oct-12	1313.40	Oct-12	236.93	Oct-12	175.40
Nov-12	305.50	Nov-12	609.15	Nov-12	1312.85	Nov-12	220.85	Nov-12	196.48
Dec-12	325.13	Dec-12	579.63	Dec-12	1258.55	Dec-12	232.85	Dec-12	197.18
Jan-13	311.75	Jan-13	697.19	Jan-13	1342.75	Jan-13	249.85	Jan-13	205.60
Feb-13	345.00	Feb-13	726.50	Feb-13	1514.75	Feb-13	261.68	Feb-13	208.25
Mar-13	360.00	Mar-13	722.48	Mar-13	1571.80	Mar-13	264.79	Mar-13	218.58
Apr-13	399.00	Apr-13	558.62	Apr-13	1376.25	Apr-13	238.63	Apr-13	173.95
May-13	361.78	May-13	601.90	May-13	1499.60	May-13	241.66	May-13	163.28
Jun-13	375.00	Jun-13	623.32	Jun-13	1518.40	Jun-13	264.78	Jun-13	174.90
Jul-13	390.00	Jul-13	741.79	Jul-13	1815.10	Jul-13	311.70	Jul-13	218.65
Aug-13	471.00	Aug-13	775.08	Aug-13	2023.15	Aug-13	344.19	Aug-13	241.95
Sep-13	517.50	Sep-13	753.87	Sep-13	1926.70	Sep-13	333.04	Sep-13	237.03
Oct-13	544.70	Oct-13	827.17	Oct-13	2108.25	Oct-13	387.60	Oct-13	238.48
Nov-13	546.75	Nov-13	838.38	Nov-13	2004.60	Nov-13	424.53	Nov-13	235.48
Dec-13	543.55	Dec-13	871.38	Dec-13	2170.95	Dec-13	459.51	Dec-13	279.53
Jan-14	635.00	Jan-14	924.87	Jan-14	2236.20	Jan-14	447.71	Jan-14	287.48
Feb-14	734.50	Feb-14	955.05	Feb-14	2272.80	Feb-14	467.65	Feb-14	298.38
Mar-14	786.50	Mar-14	819.72	Mar-14	2128.25	Mar-14	448.64	Mar-14	271.30
Apr-14	706.00	Apr-14	794.30	Apr-14	2189.40	Apr-14	458.11	Apr-14	261.00
May-14	704.80	May-14	735.38	May-14	2144.20	May-14	478.84	May-14	252.50
Jun-14	712.50	Jun-14	811.62	Jun-14	2419.45	Jun-14	538.13	Jun-14	272.48
Jul-14	750.28	Jul-14	841.43	Jul-14	2577.30	Jul-14	537.58	Jul-14	271.83
Aug-14	775.00	Aug-14	898.50	Aug-14	2524.60	Aug-14	590.50	Aug-14	282.70
Sep-14	820.00	Sep-14	936.92	Sep-14	2738.20	Sep-14	621.91	Sep-14	298.18
Oct-14	855.58	Oct-14	1012.87	Oct-14	2604.55	Oct-14	627.96	Oct-14	281.73
Nov-14	817.00	Nov-14	1089.82	Nov-14	2643.10	Nov-14	660.46	Nov-14	292.75

Dec-14	831.50	Dec-14	985.60	Dec-14	2554.70	Dec-14	647.89	Dec-14	276.90
Jan-15	798.00	Jan-15	1071.38	Jan-15	2481.00	Jan-15	719.58	Jan-15	303.15
Feb-15	900.00	Feb-15	1147.43	Feb-15	2675.30	Feb-15	716.25	Feb-15	329.63
Mar-15	1016.50	Mar-15	1108.30	Mar-15	2547.05	Mar-15	629.45	Mar-15	313.90
Apr-15	950.80	Apr-15	971.20	Apr-15	2466.65	Apr-15	623.30	Apr-15	269.28
May-15	880.00	May-15	1011.20	May-15	2610.60	May-15	554.45	May-15	280.80
Jun-15	1000.00	Jun-15	985.35	Jun-15	2552.20	Jun-15	478.20	Jun-15	272.08
Jul-15	919.75	Jul-15	1078.05	Jul-15	2510.00	Jul-15	529.60	Jul-15	284.58
Aug-15	957.00	Aug-15	1095.20	Aug-15	2565.25	Aug-15	515.60	Aug-15	285.73
Sep-15	965.00	Sep-15	1160.45	Sep-15	2587.70	Sep-15	558.05	Sep-15	298.58
Oct-15	915.00	Oct-15	1136.05	Oct-15	2497.30	Oct-15	538.90	Oct-15	286.65
Nov-15	875.00	Nov-15	1088.45	Nov-15	2365.25	Nov-15	533.40	Nov-15	286.35
Dec-15	874.10	Dec-15	1104.55	Dec-15	2439.20	Dec-15	521.60	Dec-15	279.90
Jan-16	848.00	Jan-16	1164.85	Jan-16	2391.20	Jan-16	501.55	Jan-16	280.60
Feb-16	870.00	Feb-16	1083.75	Feb-16	2181.90	Feb-16	415.05	Feb-16	259.95
Mar-16	813.25	Mar-16	1217.95	Mar-16	2516.05	Mar-16	475.45	Mar-16	281.68
Apr-16	828.90	Apr-16	1210.85	Apr-16	2530.05	Apr-16	487.20	Apr-16	276.85
May-16	752.00	May-16	1249.85	May-16	2575.10	May-16	538.40	May-16	273.10
Jun-16	741.00	Jun-16	1170.75	Jun-16	2550.80	Jun-16	506.40	Jun-16	279.18
Jul-16	735.00	Jul-16	1073.95	Jul-16	2618.55	Jul-16	486.70	Jul-16	272.65
Aug-16	752.50	Aug-16	1036.80	Aug-16	2512.55	Aug-16	468.70	Aug-16	245.25
Sep-16	783.00	Sep-16	1038.10	Sep-16	2427.20	Sep-16	419.90	Sep-16	238.83
Oct-16	802.50	Oct-16	1002.50	Oct-16	2394.60	Oct-16	439.50	Oct-16	232.50
Nov-16	768.00	Nov-16	975.45	Nov-16	2276.75	Nov-16	485.40	Nov-16	232.55
Dec-16	803.15	Dec-16	1010.70	Dec-16	2361.95	Dec-16	488.70	Dec-16	237.00

Number of 'runs' in the collected price data are identified. A 'run' means occurrence of a particular price movement followed or preceded by another kind of occurrence, e.g. increasing prices and decreasing prices are two type of 'runs'. Number of 'runs' for each type of run are counted as n_1 and n_2 .

Calculated mean runs are

$$u_r = \frac{(2n_1 n_2)}{n_1 + n_2} + 1$$

Standard Deviation of 'runs'

$$\sigma_r = \sqrt{\frac{2n_1 n_2 (2n_1 n_2 - n_1 - n_2)}{(n_1 + n_2)^2 \times (n_1 + n_2 - 1)}}$$

Whereas;

n_1 = positive sign

n_2 = negative sign

If observed number of runs is between the upper and lower limit of calculated runs at a particular level of significance then null hypothesis is accepted; otherwise rejected. We have applied the run test at 20 % Level of Significance. The value is 1.28 at 20 % level of significance.

Upper Limit = $u + 1.28 \sigma$

Lower Limit = $u - 1.28 \sigma$

Table 2: Analysis and Interpretation

Companies	Runs	n_1	n_2	Mean u	SD	Upper Limit	Lower Limit	Null Hypothesis
HCL Technologies	29	37	22	28.59	3.556	33.14	24.04	Accepted
Infosys	31	35	24	29.47	3.673	34.17	24.77	Accepted
TCS	36	31	28	30.42	3.797	35.28	25.56	Rejected
Tech Mahindra	24	34	25	29.81	3.717	34.57	25.05	Rejected
Wipro	32	31	28	30.42	3.797	35.28	25.56	Accepted

The observed runs fall between lower and upper limit for HCL Technologies, Infosys and Wipro. So, null hypothesis is accepted i.e. Price of the shares of these companies change in random. While the observed runs does not fall between the lower and upper limit for TCS and Tech Mahindra, so in these cases the null hypothesis is rejected.

Conclusion

In the case of three companies i.e. HCL Technologies, Infosys and Wipro the observed runs are falling between the upper and lower limits. So null hypothesis is accepted and supports the findings that Capital Market in India is efficient in weak form, i.e. share prices move independently of each other during successive days.

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